

Integrated Capital and Profitability of Listed Consumer Goods Firms in Nigeria

John D. Ekpoese, PhD, ACA¹ & Akamobong F. Udom, MSc, CNA²

¹Department of Accounting, University of Uyo, Uyo

¹johnekpoese@gmail.com, +2347036471244

²Department of Accountancy, Akwa Ibom State Polytechnic, Ikot Osurua

²uakamobong@gmail.com, +2348069718656

Corresponding Author: John D. Ekpoese

Abstract

Integrated capital and its effect on profitability are contemporary global corporate reporting issues following emphasis on widespread corporate failures in Nigerian organisations and reporting frameworks. This research examines the influence of integrated capital on the profitability of firms in the consumer goods sector in Nigeria. With a population of 21 firms in the consumer goods sector, a sample size of 17 companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group Plc as of 31st December, 2025, was selected using purposive sampling technique. To achieve the objectives, an ex-post facto research design was adopted involving manual generation of data from the annual reports of the selected companies. The study period was from the 2016 to 2025 financial year. The actual values of integrated capital components were generated for each of the objectives in line with the International Initiative on Integrated Reporting Council. Data obtained were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics, specifically through simple regression techniques. Integrated capital was proxied by financial, manufactured, human/intellectual, social and relationship and natural capitals, while the profitability of firms in the consumer goods sector was proxied by return on assets. Results revealed that financial, manufactured and human/intellectual capitals have a significant positive influence on return on assets; social and relationship capitals have a significant positive but weak influence on return on assets; and natural capital has a negligible positive influence on return on assets. These results were evidenced by beta

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026

ISSN: 3026-9733

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coefficients of 0.588, 0.597, 0.520, 0.342 and 0.363 and probability values of 0.000, 0.000, 0.000, 0.000 and 0.126. It was concluded that combining all the resources of the firm would contribute to the firm's profitability and generation of value in the long term. It was recommended that integrated capital should be viewed as a major area of interest in the preparation of the annual report of companies since it is rooted in international best practice in order to provide a detailed report to the provider of resources, especially the stakeholders.

Keywords: Integrated capital, Profitability, Return on Assets and Listed Consumer Goods Companies.

1. Introduction

A company's profitability serves as a measure for how well it utilises its available resources to generate revenue for its sustainability. When an organisation deploys its resources efficiently, it generally produces more money for the growth of the business. However, if corporate resources are not harnessed to their full potential, the company's survival and long-term viability are at risk, making stakeholders concerned about how to guarantee the firm's sustainability in the near future. It has been observed that for some years now, there has been bias in reporting among corporate entities. The level of skewed and biased reporting by corporate organisations and information disclosures may not ensure sound profitability and corporate sustainability. Given the recent shift in the reporting emphasis from stakeholder returns or traditional financial accounting to sustainability reporting. With an all-inclusive reporting framework, lopsided and limited reporting may make it difficult for businesses to strike a balance between corporate activities, profitability and sustainable positions.

A study conducted by Turker and Sayer (2014) suggested that financial reporting concentrates on a small percentage of the company's position and is unable to convey the impact of social and environmental aspects as well as other sustainability-related issues to interested parties. The inability to improve the entity image or assess the profitability of the organisations in accordance with societal norms and regulations or provide quantitative information about environmental hazards and opportunities

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constituted the firms' worries. The International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) introduced the Integrated Capital Reporting Framework (ICRF) as a new reporting approach in 2013 to address the issue of neglect of some vital elements in corporate reporting negligence needed to give long-term sustainability. The goal of this framework is to ensure that corporate institutions accurately disclose all forms of capital, including financial, manufactured, social and relationship, and human/intellectual, as well as natural capital, used by companies to increase or diminish their values over time. Ideally, the Integrated Capital Reporting Framework (ICRF) is required in many nations of the world for effective reporting in many companies. Hence the need for businesses to include not only the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) Framework but also the International Integrated Reporting Framework (IIRF) in their annual corporate reports and accounts, particularly when viewed from the perspective of cross-border listing. For instance, Oceanic Bank Plc and Cadbury Plc, which had achieved great financial success in the past decades, specifically in 2010, were in danger of going out of business. Similarly, the profitability of many global businesses, like Enron and WorldCom Corporation, had decreased significantly between 2001 and 2002, making them vulnerable to the effects of corporate failure. These might have happened as a result of a lack of integrated rationale in their reporting strategy.

The part of accounting procedures that provides a comprehensive assessment of a company's operations and activities is viewed as integrated capital (IC). Integrated capital uses both financial and non-financial approaches in its reporting system. However, the fundamentals of accounting have recently undergone a change from the previous financial reporting system to the present one, incorporating all capital sources such as financial, manufactured, social and relationship, and human/intellectual vis-à-vis natural into its strategy for reporting, paying attention to each component. The shortcomings of the conventional financial reporting system have received a lot of criticism. Therefore, by IC, a concise and dependable reporting method, inclusive of all capitals in the annual reports of firms. This provides an all-inclusive approach to decision-making which responds to the flaws in the long-established one-sided reporting system. Integrated capital, apart from its major goal of creating value, also exerts remarkable influence on profitability. This idea has been embraced, along with its

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Brainspec Publishers

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ISSN: 3026-9733

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guiding principles, by a number of nations that took part in the International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC) pilot programme. These nations have modified their ways of thinking to match a new reporting system.

The global financial crisis experienced in the United States of America in the 1990s brought about the idea of the International Integrated Reporting Framework (IIRF) in 2007 and was in effect from 2007 to 2009. The increasing number of investors in the capital markets and their belief in financial stability made the advent of the International Integrated Reporting Framework necessary for a vibrant economy. However, the IIRF represents a variety of interests in the development of corporate reporting wherever it is applied. The International Integrated Reporting Framework will continue to serve a variety of interests in the development of corporate reporting for as long as it is in operation.

Integrated capital is not mandatory by the Nigerian business statute or the International Financial Reporting Standards. Since the African Integrated Reporting Committee was founded in accordance with the rules of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria, integrated capital is gradually gaining ground in various African countries, including Nigeria. It is believed that a thorough strategy for wealth creation will be in place as long as integrated capital (IC) is maintained. Therefore, IC encompasses many facts, both financial and non-financial, to demonstrate how the company creates value as well as demonstrating that a company creates value both now and in the future. Although theories and research carried out in advanced nations suggest that IC increases a company's net worth, this assumption could only be verified in developing nations after widespread IC deployment. Assessing the benefit of IC may be challenging due to its subjective nature. This prompted the researcher to emphasise that, despite its contentious nature, valuation remains vital when considering societal need.

2. Statement of the Problem

Profitability remains a crucial element of any successful firm. Success in terms of profit and shareholders' wealth maximisation may not occur in the first year of adopting integrated capital reporting but may improve in subsequent years as the reporting

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approach becomes established. When all forms of capital employed in business operations are carefully accounted for in financial reports, a clearer picture of profitability can be presented in companies' annual reports. However, the profitability of most companies remains obscured due to the exclusion or limited disclosure of sustainable capital in corporate annual reports. Profitability evaluation would be more straightforward if all forms of capital were considered concurrently in companies' reports.

The amount of capital used by a company to create value does not always directly correspond with its level of financial success. This is because economic theories and business practices have historically been dominated by financial and manufactured capital. This raises the question of whether these two forms of capital are the only resources through which businesses create value over time. Such an approach may be at the expense of integrated capital, as stakeholders have expressed concern over the continued emphasis on financial and manufactured capital and the limited disclosure of sustainable capitals, such as human/intellectual, social and relationship, and natural capital, in companies' annual reports. Consequently, it remains uncertain whether the reporting of only financial and manufactured capital is sufficient to enhance long-term profitability and sustain business operations.

Beyond serving as a reporting framework, integrated capital represents a more comprehensive approach to improving firms' profitability and is believed to exert a greater influence on value creation. Prior studies conducted in countries such as the United States, the Netherlands, Japan, and South Africa have shown that value creation is central to sustaining corporate profitability. Much of the existing research has focused on corporate finance and firm value, yielding mixed results. Other studies have examined selected components of integrated capital, such as structural capital, and their influence on profitability using longitudinal and mixed research approaches, firm characteristics, cost of capital, and least squares estimation techniques. However, the findings of these studies remain inconclusive despite the use of diverse analytical methods, concepts, and theoretical frameworks.

Studies on integrated capital and its influence on profitability are relatively scarce in the context of Nigerian listed consumer goods firms. Where integrated capital

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Brainspec Publishers

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may have influenced the profitability of such firms, this influence has not been clearly documented. Against this background, the present study examined the influence of integrated capital on the profitability of consumer goods firms in Nigeria, measured by return on assets. The fundamental hypothesis of the study is that integrated capital has no significant influence on the profitability of consumer goods firms. This assumption is further specified for analytical purposes as stated below:

- H₀1: There is no significant influence of financial capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.
- H₀2: Manufactured capital does not have a significant influence on the return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.
- H₀3: There is no significant influence of human/intellectual capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.
- H₀4: Social and relationship capital does not have a significant influence on the return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.
- H₀5: There is no significant influence of natural capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

3.1 Theoretical Framework

Corporate reporting is an ever-evolving field, as companies continually strive to improve communication with their stakeholders. One of the most important ways of achieving this is through integrated reporting, which culminates in the annual integrated report. Integrated reporting seeks to align relevant information about an organization's strategy, governance, performance, and future prospects in a manner that reflects the economic, environmental, and social context in which it operates. It is primarily aimed at explaining to providers of capital how an organization creates value over time through the effective use of different forms of capital.

The International Integrated Reporting Council (IIRC, 2013) identified six forms of capital used in integrated reporting, namely: financial capital, manufactured capital, human capital, intellectual capital, social and relationship capital, and natural capital. Ajekwe (2019) conceptualized these capitals as money, goods, labour, ideas, and relationships with nature, noting that they are transformed through organizational

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activities to generate value. For instance, profitability enhances financial and manufactured capital; human and intellectual capital improve through employee training and skills development; and natural capital is sustained through environmentally responsible practices.

Every firm employs a combination of these capitals in producing goods or services. Value creation is therefore multifaceted, extending beyond share price, profit, and growth to include sustainability and long-term viability. However, internal mechanisms and externalities, such as supply chains, community relations, and environmental impacts, may undermine value creation. Since integrated reporting encompasses environmental stewardship, social reputation, human resources, financial strength, and physical assets, integrated capital consists of diverse but interconnected resources (Ajekwe, 2019). Accordingly, the categories of integrated capital identified by the IIRC (2013) include financial, manufactured, human/intellectual, social and relationship, and natural capital.

Financial capital refers to the pool of funds available to an organization for use in the production of goods or the provision of services. These funds may be obtained through financing activities such as debt, equity, or grants, or generated internally through operations and investments.

Manufactured capital comprises physical objects distinct from natural resources that are used in the production of goods or services. These include buildings, machinery, equipment, and infrastructure such as roads, bridges, ports, and water or waste treatment facilities. Manufactured capital may be created by other organizations or by the reporting entity itself for sale or internal use.

Human and intellectual capital encompass employees' competencies, capabilities, experience, and motivation to innovate. This includes their alignment with organizational governance structures, ethical values, and risk management systems, as well as their ability to develop and implement strategy. Intellectual capital also covers organizational knowledge-based intangibles such as patents, copyrights, software, licenses, tacit knowledge, systems, procedures, and protocols.

Social and relationship capital consists of institutions, relationships, and networks within and between communities and stakeholder groups. It includes shared

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norms, values, behaviours, trust, and the willingness to engage, as well as intangible assets such as brand reputation and social licence to operate.

Natural capital refers to renewable and non-renewable environmental resources and ecosystem processes that support an organization's past, present, and future prosperity. These include air, water, land, minerals, forests, biodiversity, and ecosystem health.

Return on Assets (ROA) measures the efficiency with which a firm utilizes its assets to generate earnings. It is calculated by dividing profit before interest and taxes by total assets (Ewereoke, 2018). Suresh (2018) noted that ROA reflects the revenue generated per unit of asset employed. A rising ROA indicates improved operational efficiency and performance. Although several performance measures exist, ROA is particularly useful for comparing firms within the same industry. Consequently, this study adopts ROA as a measure of firm performance among listed Nigerian consumer goods firms.

The relationship between integrated capital and profitability can be explained using stakeholder theory. The foundations of stakeholder theory were initially proposed by Mary Parker Follett and later developed by Freeman (1984). According to Freeman (1984), a stakeholder is any individual or group that can affect or is affected by the achievement of an organization's objectives. Stakeholders may be direct, such as shareholders, employees, customers, suppliers, and investors, or indirect, such as government and society at large (Schilling, 2000).

Stakeholder theory recognizes the complex and dynamic relationships between organizations and their stakeholders, emphasizing responsibility and accountability (Gray et al., 1996). The theory incorporates both ethical and managerial dimensions. Ethically, it advocates fair treatment of all stakeholders, while managerially, it recognizes that firms may prioritize more powerful stakeholders who are critical to organizational survival. Integrated reporting therefore seeks to meet the diverse information needs of stakeholders by providing comprehensive disclosures (Adegbayegun et al., 2020; Camilleri, 2018).

Clarke (2004) viewed organizations as multilateral agreements between firms and their stakeholders, governed by both formal and informal rules developed over

time. While shareholders provide capital, firms depend on employees for productivity and other stakeholders for legitimacy and sustainability. Consequently, corporate focus has expanded beyond shareholders to include social, environmental, and ethical considerations (Donaldson & Preston, 1995; Freeman, 1984). Stakeholder theory is therefore suitable for this study as it emphasizes long-term organizational survival, value creation, and balanced consideration of stakeholder interests in the deployment of integrated capital.

3.2 Literature Review

Akbar et al. (2023) examined the sustainability of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) competitiveness in Bogor City, Indonesia, using entrepreneurial orientation, financial capital, and innovation as explanatory variables. Employing a survey research design and multiple regression analysis, data were collected from 384 MSME owners and managers. The findings revealed that entrepreneurial orientation, financial capital, and innovation had positive and significant effects on MSME competitiveness. The study recommended that policymakers and stakeholders enhance MSMEs' access to finance, innovation capabilities, and entrepreneurial skills to sustain competitiveness.

Wang et al. (2023) investigated the legacy environmental footprints of manufactured capital using 50 years of global economic and environmental data. Adopting an ex-post facto research design, the study employed regression analysis and dynamic stock modelling to assess environmental stresses linked to manufactured capital accumulation. The results showed that environmental footprints grew faster than GDP and population between 1995 and 2019, with disproportionate impacts on developing economies. The study concluded that sustainable asset production practices are necessary to mitigate environmental damage and global inequality.

Amos and Oboh (2023) examined the effect of human capital reporting on stock market performance in Nigeria's services sector from 2016 to 2020. Using an ex-post facto design and fixed-effects hierarchical regression, the study found that human capital acquisition, training, and development had a positive and significant effect on stock market performance. However, human capital compensation and welfare

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ROA = $f(\text{FC})$	Hypothesis one
ROA = $f(\text{MC})$	Hypothesis two
ROA = $f(\text{H/IC})$	Hypothesis three
ROA = $f(\text{S\&RC})$	Hypothesis four
ROA = $f(\text{NC})$	Hypothesis five

Substituting profitability and integrated capital variables in a regression statistics equation, the following model were developed thus:

$\text{ROA}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{FC})_{it} + e_{it}$	-	-	-	-	-	Equation 3.2
$\text{ROA}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{MC})_{it} + e_{it}$	-	-	-	-	-	-Equation 3.3
$\text{ROA}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{H/IC})_{it} + e_{it}$	-	-	-	-	-	Equation 3.4
$\text{ROA}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{S\&RC})_{it} + e_{it}$	-	-	-	-	-	Equation 3.5
$\text{ROA}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{NC})_{it} + e_{it}$	-	-	-	-	-	-Equation 3.6

Where:

ROA	=	Return on Assets
β_0	=	Constant Terms
β_1	=	Estimated Coefficients of the independent variables
FC	=	Financial Capital
MC	=	Manufactured Capital
H/IC	=	Human/Intellectual Capital
S\&RC	=	Social and Relationship Capital
NC	=	Natural Capital
e	=	Error term
i	=	Number of Companies
t	=	Number of years

5. Data Analyses and Findings

The hypotheses were tested through simple regression analysis using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 25.0 at 5% level of significance. However, results are stated as follows:

Table 4.1: Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness	Kurtosis		
	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Statistics	Std. Error	Statistics	Std. Error
Profitability (ROA)(%)	170	-235.99	617.43	7.5224	57.84140	7.447	.186	80.110	.370
Financial Capital(N'000)	170	57,257.00	673,011,809.00	121,854,318.4647	156,010,096.24921	1.536	.186	1.494	.370
Manufactured Capital(N'000)	170	43,388.00	358,967,704.00	59,121,507.5765	77,666,464.92247	1.508	.186	1.387	.370
Human/Intellectual Capital(N'000)	170	20,160.00	51,338,482.00	8,208,254.0118	11,178,469.17041	1.919	.186	3.208	.370
Social/Relationship Capital(N'000)	170	.00	47,545,560.00	647,777.4000	3,868,674.47684	10.845	.186	129.676	.370
Natural Capital(N'000)	170	.00	33,811.00	734.0706	3,574.45412	7.042	.186	56.160	.370
Valid N (listwise)	170								

Source: Researcher's Computation (2026)

Table 4.1 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the study. Profitability, which was proxied by return on assets, was the dependent variable in the study. From Table 4.1, return on assets has a minimum value of -235.99% and a maximum value of 617.43% . It also has a mean value of 7.5224% with a standard deviation of 57.84140% , indicating variability in profitability. This signifies that the mean and standard deviation deviated by 50.319% . However, the coefficient of skewness of 7.447% implies that the data are positively skewed, tilted towards the right tail of the distribution, and leptokurtic in nature, as the kurtosis value stood at 80.110% . This indicates a highly peaked distribution with a thin bell shape and heavy tails, which meets acceptable criteria.

Financial capital was represented by total debt and equity in the study. Table 4.1 indicates that the minimum and maximum values of financial capital (total debt and equity) were $\text{N}57,257.00$ and $\text{N}673,011,809.00$, respectively, with a mean value of $\text{N}121,854,318.4647$ and a standard deviation of $\text{N}156,010,096.24921$. This shows a dispersion between the mean and standard deviation of total debt and equity capital. The coefficient of skewness of 1.536 implies that total debt and equity capital are positively skewed and tilted towards the right tail of the distribution. The kurtosis value of 1.494 suggests that total debt and equity are leptokurtic in nature and meet normal distribution criteria.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026

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Manufactured capital was represented by property, plant, and equipment in the study. Table 4.1 indicates that the minimum and maximum values of manufactured capital (property, plant, and equipment) were ₦43,388.00 and ₦358,967,704.00, respectively, with a mean value of ₦59,121,509.5765 and a standard deviation of ₦77,666,464.92247. This shows a dispersion between the mean and standard deviation of property, plant, and equipment. The coefficient of skewness of 1.508 implies that property, plant, and equipment are positively skewed and tilted towards the right tail of the distribution. The kurtosis value of 1.387 suggests that property, plant, and equipment are leptokurtic in nature and meet acceptable distribution criteria.

Human/intellectual capital was represented by personnel costs in the study. Table 4.1 indicates that the minimum and maximum values of human/intellectual capital (personnel costs) were ₦20,160.00 and ₦51,338,482.00, respectively, with a mean value of ₦8,208,254.0118 and a standard deviation of ₦11,178,469.17041. This shows a dispersion between the mean and standard deviation of personnel costs. The coefficient of skewness of 1.919 implies that personnel costs are positively skewed and tilted towards the right tail of the distribution. The kurtosis value of 3.208 suggests that personnel costs are leptokurtic in nature and meet acceptable distribution criteria.

Social and relationship capital was represented by donations in the study. Table 4.1 indicates that the minimum and maximum values of social and relationship capital (donations) were ₦0.00 and ₦47,545,560.00, respectively, with a mean value of ₦647,777.40000 and a standard deviation of ₦3,868,674.47684. This shows a dispersion between the mean and standard deviation of donations. The coefficient of skewness of 10.845 implies that donations are positively skewed and tilted towards the right tail of the distribution. The kurtosis value of 129.676 suggests that donations are highly peaked with a thin bell shape and heavy tails, indicating a leptokurtic distribution that meets acceptable criteria.

Natural capital was represented by environmental costs in the study. Table 4.1 indicates that the minimum and maximum values of natural capital (environmental costs) were ₦0.00 and ₦33,811.00, respectively, with a mean value of ₦734.0706 and a standard deviation of ₦3,574.45412. This shows a dispersion between the mean and standard deviation of environmental costs. The coefficient of skewness of 7.042 implies

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Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026

ISSN: 3026-9733

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that environmental costs are positively skewed and tilted towards the right tail of the distribution. The kurtosis value of 56.160 suggests that environmental costs are highly peaked with a thin bell shape and heavy tails, indicating a leptokurtic distribution that meets acceptable criteria.

Test of Hypotheses

The test was carried out using ordinary least square regression with the model specification shown below using Statistical Package for Social Science version 25.0 software. The result of the analysis is shown in the study below.

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of financial capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Table 4.2: Summary.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.588 ^a	.346	.342	.78221	1.573

a. Predictor: (Constant), Financial Capital. b. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.3: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	54.413	1	54.413	88.931	.000 ^b
1	Residual	102.792	168	.612		
	Total	157.206	169			

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability. b. Predictor: (Constant), Financial Capital

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

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Table 4.4: Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error				Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.105	.454		4.636	.000		
	Financial Capital	.567	.060	.588	9.430	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability.

Source: *Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)*

Table 4.2 presents the summary of the influence of financial capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The R-square value of 0.346 indicates that 34.6% of the variation in return on assets of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria is explained by financial capital in the regression model. Table 4.3 shows a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis one was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. Thus, there is a significant positive influence of financial capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, in line with the decision rule of the study. This was further confirmed by the calculated t-value of 9.430 against the critical t-value of 1.962. Table 4.4 shows a beta coefficient of 0.588 for financial capital, implying that, holding other variables constant, an increase in financial capital leads to a corresponding increase in return on assets. Specifically, a ₦1 increase in financial capital would result in a ₦0.588 increase in return on assets.

H₀: Manufactured capital does not have a significant influence on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026

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Table 4.5: Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.597 ^a	.356	.352	.77631	1.587

a. Predictor: (Constant), Manufactured Capital. b. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.6: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	55.959	1	55.959	92.854	.000 ^b
1 Residual	101.246	168	.603		
Total	157.206	169			

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability. b. Predictor: (Constant), Manufactured Capital

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.7: Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	2.312	.423		5.462	.000		
	Manufactured Capital	.567	.059	.597	9.636	.000	1.000	1.000

b. Dependent Variable: Profitability.

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.5 presents the summary of the influence of manufactured capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The R-square value of 0.356 indicates that 35.6% of the variation in return on assets of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria is explained by manufactured capital in the regression model. Table 4.6

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shows a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis two was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. Thus, there is a significant positive influence of manufactured capital on return on assets of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, in line with the decision rule of the study. This was further confirmed by the calculated t-value of 9.636 against the critical t-value of 1.962. Table 4.7 shows a beta coefficient of 0.597 for manufactured capital, implying that, holding other variables constant, an increase in manufactured capital leads to a corresponding increase in return on assets. Specifically, a ₦1 increase in manufactured capital would result in a ₦0.597 increase in return on assets.

H₀: There is no significant influence between human/intellectual capital and return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Table 4.8: Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.520 ^a	.271	.266	.82611	1.525

a. Predictor: (Constant), Human/Intellectual Capital. b. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.9: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	42.553	1	42.553	62.352	.000 ^b
1	Residual	114.653	168	.682		
	Total	157.206	169			

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability. b. Predictor: (Constant), Human/Intellectual Capital

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.10: Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		Coefficients		Coefficients			Tolerance	VIF
		B	Std. Error	Beta				
	(Constant)	2.809	.453		6.202	.000		
1	Human/Intellectual Capital	.557	.071	.520	7.896	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.8 presents the summary of the influence of human/intellectual capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The R-square value of 0.271 indicates that 27.1% of the variation in return on assets of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria is explained by human/intellectual capital in the regression model. Table 4.9 shows a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis three was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. Thus, there is a significant influence of human/intellectual capital on return on assets of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, in line with the decision rule of the study. This was further confirmed by the calculated t-value of 7.896 against the critical t-value of 1.962. Table 4.10 shows a beta coefficient of 0.520 for human/intellectual capital, implying that, holding other variables constant, an increase in human/intellectual capital leads to a corresponding increase in return on assets. Specifically, a ₦1 increase in human/intellectual capital would result in a ₦0.520 increase in return on assets.

H₀: Social and relationship capital does not have a significant influence on listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026

ISSN: 3026-9733

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Table 4.11: Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.342 ^a	.117	.109	.77971	1.522

a. Predictor: (Constant), Social and Relationship Capital. b. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.12: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	8.530	1	8.530	14.031	.000 ^b
	Residual	64.443	168	.608		
	Total	72.974	169			

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability. b. Predictor: (Constant), Social and Relationship Capital

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.13: Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	5.259	.347		15.159	.000		
	Social/Relationship Capital	.272	.072	.342	3.746	.000	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.11 presents the summary of the influence of social and relationship capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The R-square value of 0.117 indicates that 11.7% of the variation in return on assets of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria is explained by social and relationship capital in the

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INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026

ISSN: 3026-9733

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regression model. Table 4.12 shows a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis four was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. Thus, there is a significant positive influence of social and relationship capital on return on assets of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, in line with the decision rule of the study. This was further confirmed by the calculated t-value of 3.746 against the critical t-value of 1.962. Table 4.13 shows a beta coefficient of 0.342 for social and relationship capital, implying that, holding other variables constant, an increase in social and relationship capital leads to a corresponding increase in return on assets. Specifically, a ₦1 increase in social and relationship capital would result in a ₦0.342 increase in return on assets.

Ho₅: There is no significant influence of natural capital on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria.

Table 4.14: Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.363 ^a	.132	.081	.48328	1.408

a. Predictor: (Constant), Natural Capital. b. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.15: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	.603	1	.603	2.583	.126 ^b
1	Residual	3.970	168	.234		
	Total	4.574	169			

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability. b. Predictor: (Constant), Natural Capital

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.16: Coefficient

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	Coefficients		Coefficients			Tolerance	VIF
	B	Std. Error	Beta				
(Constant)	6.233	.500		12.474	.000		
1 Natural Capital	.234	.145	.363	1.607	.126	1.000	1.000

a. Dependent Variable: Profitability

Source: Researcher's Analytical Output (2026)

Table 4.14 presents the summary of the influence of natural capital on the return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The R-square value of 0.132 indicates that 13.2% of the variation in return on assets of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria is explained by natural capital in the regression model. Table 4.15 shows a p-value of 0.126, which is greater than 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis five was accepted and the alternative hypothesis rejected. Thus, there is no significant influence of natural capital on return on assets of the listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, which is not in line with the decision rule of the study. This was further confirmed by the calculated t-value of 1.607 against the critical t-value of 1.962. Table 4.16 shows a beta coefficient of 0.363 for natural capital, implying that, holding other variables constant, an increase in natural capital would lead to an increase in return on assets of that magnitude. Specifically, a ₦1 increase in natural capital would result in a ₦0.363 increase in return on assets, although this effect is not statistically significant.

6. Discussion of Findings

Inspired by the quest to determine whether integrated capital influences the profitability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria, integrated capital was stratified into financial capital, manufactured capital, human/intellectual capital, social and relationship capital, as well as natural capital dimensions. In line with these classifications, five hypotheses were developed and analyzed. Data for the variables across seventeen listed

IJCITR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CONTEMPORARY ISSUES AND TRENDS IN RESEARCH

Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026

ISSN: 3026-9733

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consumer goods firms over a period of ten years were computed and analyzed, and the results are discussed below.

In line with hypothesis one, financial capital, with a t-statistic of 9.430 and a probability value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), and a regression coefficient of 0.588, demonstrated a positive and significant influence on return on assets of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. This implies that financial capital has a positive and significant influence on the profitability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The analysis further implies that a unit increase in financial capital will cause about ₦58.80 increase in return on assets of the sector. This suggests that integrated capital reflects the challenges and uncertainties organizations are likely to encounter in pursuing their strategies and the potential implications for business models and future performance. This finding agrees with the *a priori* expectation of the variable, which was proposed based on earlier studies. It is also consistent with the findings of Asemota and Igweagbara (2023), who reported a positive and significant influence of institutional qualities on financial capital inflows in Nigerian institutions from 1996 to 2021.

In line with hypothesis two, manufactured capital, with a t-statistic of 9.636 and a probability value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), and a regression coefficient of 0.597, demonstrated a significant positive influence on return on assets. This implies that manufactured capital has a positive and significant influence on the profitability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The analysis indicates that a unit increase in manufactured capital will cause about ₦59.70 increase in return on assets of the sector. This infers that incorporating existing resources in a concise manner helps communicate how an organization's strategy, governance, performance, and prospects, within the context of its external environment, lead to value creation. This finding agrees with the *a priori* expectation of the variable and aligns with the study of Wang et al. (2023), who asserted a significant positive effect of manufactured capital on legacy environmental footprints of 200 manufacturing industries from 1995 to 2019.

In line with hypothesis three, human/intellectual capital, with a t-statistic of 7.896 and a probability value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), and a regression coefficient of 0.520, demonstrated a significant positive influence on return on assets. This indicates that human/intellectual capital positively influences the profitability of listed consumer

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Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026

ISSN: 3026-9733

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goods firms in Nigeria. The analysis implies that a unit increase in human/intellectual capital will cause about ₦52.00 increase in return on assets of the sector. This suggests that enterprise viability and assumptions in reporting an entity's capital are critical, such that adverse conditions signal challenges, and firms are expected to possess the capacity to sustain operations in the long term rather than face short-term liquidation. This finding agrees with the *a priori* expectation of the variable and is consistent with the findings of Amos and Oboh (2023), who reported a significant influence of human capital reporting on firms' stock market performance among 24 publicly traded companies in Nigeria from 2016 to 2020.

Hypothesis four, with a t-statistic of 3.746, a probability value of 0.000 (less than 0.05), and a regression coefficient of 0.342, demonstrated a weak but significant positive influence of social and relationship capital on return on assets. This implies that social and relationship capital has a positive but weak influence on the profitability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The analysis further implies that a unit increase in social and relationship capital will cause about ₦34.20 increase in return on assets of the sector. This assumes that incorporating existing resources in a succinct manner enhances communication of how an organization's strategy, governance, performance, and prospects contribute to value creation. This finding agrees with the *a priori* expectation of the variable and aligns with Nguyen et al. (2019), who reported a significant relationship between relational capital and supply chain collaboration for radical and incremental innovations among 225 vendors in China between 2015 and 2016.

In line with hypothesis five, natural capital, with a t-statistic of 1.607 and a probability value of 0.126 (greater than 0.05), and a regression coefficient of 0.363, demonstrated a positive but insignificant influence on return on assets. This indicates that natural capital has a positive but statistically insignificant influence on the profitability of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The analysis implies that a unit increase in natural capital will cause about ₦36.30 increase in return on assets of the sector. This suggests that enterprise viability and assumptions in reporting an entity's capital are important indicators of long-term sustainability, even when short-term profitability effects are insignificant. This finding disagrees with the *a priori*

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Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026

ISSN: 3026-9733

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expectation of the variable. However, it aligns with Etim et al. (2022), who reported an insignificant negative influence of environmental/natural capital reporting on the profitability of 23 manufacturing companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group Plc from 2008 to 2017.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

Drawing from the test results, the researchers concluded that there is a significant positive influence of financial, manufactured, social and relationship, and human capitals on return on assets of consumer goods companies in Nigeria, while natural capital exerted a positive but negligible influence on return on assets. Consequently, the researchers recommended as follows:

- i. Regulatory authorities should require integrated capital reporting rather than allowing listed companies to opt out, since these capitals serve as the company's growth engine and have a positive effect on stakeholders in Nigeria.
- ii. Accounting standard-setters and regulators on integrated capital should implement integrated capital reporting to the fullest. This would serve as a boost to listed consumer goods firms and help them move away from the traditional method of reporting towards global best practices.
- iii. The Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria should encourage quoted firms in Nigeria to move from voluntary integrated reporting to international best practices in reporting methods.
- iv. Listed companies in Nigeria should be monitored for non-adherence to integrated reporting practices, and appropriate sanctions should be imposed on defaulters.
- v. More investment should be put in place by consumer goods firms, as it forms the foundation for a thriving business and society and is directly linked to a company's profitability.

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Brainspec Publishers

VOLUME 4, ISSUE 1, JANUARY, 2026
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